
SCALE, ORDER, AND SPECTRAL ANALYSIS IN PHONONIC METAMATERIALS

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March 8, 2026

ABSTRACT

We investigate localization and band structure for quasistatic elastic waves in two-dimensional viscoelastic composites consisting of circular inclusions within a host matrix. Using the analytic continuation method of homogenization, we demonstrate a transition in the spectral properties of a key self-adjoint operator G that mirrors Anderson localization behavior. As inclusion size increases in disordered arrangements, the eigenvalue spacing distribution transitions from Wigner-Dyson to Poisson statistics, accompanied by increased eigenstate localization. In periodic arrangements, we observe clear band structure through sharp resonances in the spectral measure and effective complex shear modulus μ^* , with mobility edges separating extended and localized eigenstates. Moreover, the phase of μ^* undergoes sharp switches from near 0° to 180° at resonant frequencies, signaling transitions from elastic energy-storing response to a regime characterized by a negative effective shear modulus. These features disappear in disordered systems, where resonances in the spectral measure broaden, eigenstates and physical fields are typically more localized and associated mobility edges are less pronounced. Our results reveal how composite microstructure governs wave transport properties through an interplay between geometric order, inclusion size, and material impedance contrast, providing insights for designing materials with tailored elastic wave propagation characteristics.

Keywords Phononic crystals · Anderson localization · Homogenization · Random matrix theory

1 Introduction

Anderson localization (AL), first discovered in the context of electron transport in disordered systems, has since been observed across a wide range of classical wave phenomena Legendijk et al. [2009]. AL of waves arises from the interference of multiple scattering paths in sufficiently disordered media. For classical scalar and vector waves, AL can occur in electromagnetic, acoustic, water, and seismic waves, among others. AL can be measured using multiple mathematical methods, including the self-consistent theory of localization, transfer matrix methods, and multifractal analysis (see, e.g., Sheng [2006]). Recent studies have demonstrated AL in various systems, from random three-dimensional networks of aluminum spheres Hu et al. [2008a] to acoustic wave propagation in disordered crystals Yang et al. [2023].

Phononic crystals (PCs), materials featuring periodic heterogeneity in their elastic properties, can exhibit band gaps – frequency ranges where wave propagation is forbidden – leading to effective sound absorption and vibration isolation

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effects Sigalas and Economou [1993], Liu et al. [2020]. Along with band gaps, exotic properties such as negative refractive, shear, and bulk moduli with enhanced sound absorption can occur in PCs Ma and Sheng [2016], Wu et al. [2011], Ke et al. [2005], Hu et al. [2008b], Nemat-Nasser [2019]. The characteristics of these band gaps are notably influenced by geometric parameters, such as the ratio of slab thickness to lattice constant in PC slabs Khelif et al. [2006], while altering the hole arrangement and porosity patterning leads to tuned PCs with certain desired characteristics Shim et al. [2015]. As disorder is introduced into the composite, the PC band structure is replaced by increased localization effects Yang et al. [2023], Wang et al. [2019], particularly for transverse wave propagation in waveguides Ye et al. [2015]. The effect of viscoelasticity on PC band structure is covered in Merheb et al. [2009].

There is rich theory surrounding the localization of classical waves in disordered systems Sheng and Zhang [1986], Condat and Kirkpatrick [1990], Thouless [2010]. In Figotin and Klein [1996], it was shown that a random self-adjoint acoustic operator A exhibits AL inside the gap in the spectrum of its periodic counterpart A_0 . Particularly noteworthy is the finding that elastic waves exhibit a disorder-induced localization transition belonging to the same orthogonal universality class as spinless electrons in three-dimensional disordered potentials Skipetrov and Beltukov [2018].

In this work, we investigate viscoelastic two-dimensional periodic and disordered arrangements of circular inclusions within a host matrix and explore the effects of the lattice constant a and constituent material impedance contrast on quasistatic elastic wave propagation and the effective complex shear modulus (or viscoelasticity) μ^* . Our analysis employs the analytic continuation method (ACM) of homogenization for electromagnetic Bergman [1980], Milton [1980], Golden and Papanicolaou [1983], Milton [2002] and viscoelastic Cherkhev and Bonifasi-Lista [2011], Cherkhev [2019] problems; this method introduces an important self-adjoint operator G (defined in Section 2.2) and its spectral measure ν . The spectral properties of G reveal fascinating insights into the interactions between material microgeometry and wave physics, essentially playing a role analogous to the Hamiltonian in quantum physics, but for classical transport. The spectral properties of G have been used to investigate the geometric drivers of electromagnetic AL and band structure in periodic and quasiperiodic composites Murphy et al. [2017], Morison et al. [2022]. In discrete settings, G is a real-symmetric matrix. The measure ν , local deformation field ϵ , and stress $\sigma = \mathbf{C} : \epsilon$ are all determined by the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of G .

Our results reveal that the characteristic scale of inclusions in disordered composites determines an Anderson-like transition in the spectral properties of G despite the absence of any wave interference, scattering, or quantum phenomena. We find that as the inclusion sizes become smaller, the eigenvalues of G shift from weakly correlated Poisson-like statistics toward highly correlated universal Wigner-Dyson statistics of the Gaussian Orthogonal Ensemble (GOE). This transition mirrors AL, with the characteristic size of inclusions playing a role analogous to the critical disorder level necessary for localization in wave physics Sheng and Zhang [1986]. These results indicate that larger inclusions induce localized strain modes, while smaller inclusions result in a collection of more extended modes, i.e., the deformation magnitude is allowed to spread out and utilize more avenues to distribute its energy. The broadening of spectral resonances in disordered systems is reflected in the effective viscoelasticity μ^* , where the systematic phase and modulus structure seen in periodic systems is replaced by an irregular response lacking frequency selectivity. We also observe band structure in periodic microgeometries through localization of the deformation field ϵ and resonances in μ^* . Spectral measures for periodic systems have sharp resonances that induce dramatic variability in band and absorption characteristics, and in profiles of μ^* . Regions of extended eigenstates are separated by "mobility edges" of localized states, and the strain field is localized for certain frequencies and extended for others. At resonant frequencies, the phase of μ^* undergoes sharp switches from near 0° to 180° , signaling transitions from elastic energy-storing response to a regime characterized by a negative effective shear modulus, with these features becoming more pronounced as system size increases. These results suggest that by tuning the geometric order, inclusion scale, and material contrast, one can design viscoelastic composites with targeted frequency-selective vibration isolation through band gaps, broadband energy trapping through disorder-induced localization, or controlled phase profiles of μ^* that govern the balance between energy storage and dissipation.

2 Methods

2.1 Material geometry and scaling

We consider here both ordered (periodic) and disordered (random) arrangements of circular inclusions, keeping in mind the large parameter space for possible phononic crystal geometries available for future study. For ordered systems, the inclusions are arranged in a square lattice with varying lattice constant $a = L_{\text{cell}}/L$. For instance, $a = 1$ corresponds to a single circular inclusion, while $a = 1/5$ corresponds to a 5×5 grid of inclusions. We study the effects of the lattice for the values $a \in \{1/2, 1/5, 1/15\}$ on the localization properties of the deviatoric (volume-preserving) component of strain ϵ_s and the spectral properties of G . In addition to periodic arrangements of circular inclusions, we repeat the same experiments for disordered circular inclusions. For each lattice constant a , the radii of inclusions between both

Figure 1: **Periodic and disordered arrangements of circles in a host matrix.** (a) A single unit cell with side length L_{cell} . The radii of the inclusions are taken to ensure that $\phi \approx 0.3$ in all cases. (b) A periodic arrangement of circles with lattice constant $a = L_{\text{cell}}/L = 0.2$ and $r = La\sqrt{0.3/\pi}$. (c) A disordered arrangement of circles with the same circle radii as (b). The volume fraction $\phi = 0.2521 \lesssim 0.3$ is due to the periodic and random constraints for constructing the geometry. Although this disordered geometry is not a lattice and hence does not have a lattice constant a , we associate with it the lattice constant $a = 0.2$ because it shares the same circle radii and similar filling fraction as the lattice in (b). We maintain similar correspondence between periodic and disordered geometries, using the lattice constant a to refer to both types. Note that for $a = 1$, the periodic and random geometries are merely translated versions of each other.

the periodic and disordered geometries are kept the same. The packing fraction ϕ , defined as the fraction of the total area of inclusions, is held constant at $\phi \approx 0.3$ across all geometries to ensure that results solely pertain to the effects of a and the geometric arrangement of inclusions. The disordered geometries are generated using the MATLAB function *bubblebath* Danz [2020] which randomly places circles in a square region with an approximate filling fraction $\phi \approx 0.3$ as well as periodic boundary conditions. These geometries are displayed in Figure 1. An important consideration is that the fixed filling fraction ϕ ensures that the different lattice constants a investigated here have an equivalent interpretation as scaling factors, i.e., a lattice constant of $a = 1/15$ is a scaled version of the same geometry for $a = 1/2$ for both periodic and random geometries, respectively.

The scaling theory of wave localization Sheng [2006] helps bridge the gap between classical and quantum mechanical waves in mesoscopic processes. The wave transport properties of systems across scales can be analyzed using the scaling parameters β and γ . Here, $\gamma = \delta\omega/\Delta\omega$ represents the ratio of the Thouless time $\delta\omega$ (the time for a wave to traverse the system) to the mean level spacing $\Delta\omega$ (the average frequency separation between neighboring eigenmodes). The scaling function $\beta(\gamma) = d \ln \gamma / d \ln L$, where d is dimension, describes how γ changes with system size L or geometric scaling. The parameter γ is closely related to the Thouless conductance g , which quantifies the system's ability to transmit waves and provides a measure of the transition from localized to extended behavior as the system size changes. In the current setting, the Thouless conductance g is in turn related to the effective shear modulus μ^* of a heterogeneous material. In Section 3.2, we will infer how the scaling function β qualitatively changes with respect to geometric order and scale in this class of phononic metamaterials.

2.2 Stieltjes integral and resolvent representations

Consider mechanical S (shear) waves in two phase composites in the absence of internal forces, where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ are the stress and strain fields satisfying $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, $\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = 0$, \mathbf{C} is the fourth-rank local elasticity/stiffness tensor, and (\cdot) denotes tensor contraction. The strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is a symmetrized gradient ∇^S of the displacement \vec{u} ,

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \nabla^S \vec{u} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \vec{u} + \nabla \vec{u}^T) = \begin{bmatrix} \partial_1 u_1 & \frac{1}{2}(\partial_1 u_2 + \partial_2 u_1) \\ \frac{1}{2}(\partial_1 u_2 + \partial_2 u_1) & \partial_2 u_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\partial_k = \partial/\partial x_k$ for Cartesian coordinates x_1, x_2 . For two-phase composite materials, we assign the elasticity \mathbf{C}_1 to the first phase of the material and \mathbf{C}_2 to the second phase. The elasticity tensor can then be written as $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}_1 \chi_1 + \mathbf{C}_2 \chi_2$, where $\chi_1 = 1$ in medium 1 and is zero otherwise, with $\chi_2 = 1 - \chi_1$. We assume that each phase of the material is locally isotropic which allows us to separate the volumetric and deviatoric components of the elasticity tensor as Milton [2002]

$$\mathbf{C} = 2K\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_h + 2\mu\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_s, \quad (2)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_h = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_{ij}\delta_{kl}), \quad \boldsymbol{\Lambda}_s = \frac{1}{2}(\delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \delta_{il}\delta_{jk} - \delta_{ij}\delta_{kl}), \quad (3)$$

where K is the bulk elastic modulus, μ is the complex shear modulus, and $\mathbf{\Lambda}_h$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}_s$ are orthogonal projections onto volumetric and deviatoric spaces, respectively. The volumetric space of second rank 2×2 matrices consists of shape-preserving deformations, which are multiples of the identity, and the deviatoric space consists of trace-free, volume-preserving deformations. Applying this decomposition to $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ reveals the simple relations between the volumetric and deviatoric components of stress and strain:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_h = 2K\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_h, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s = 2\mu\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s, \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_h = \mathbf{\Lambda}_h\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s = \mathbf{\Lambda}_s\boldsymbol{\epsilon}. \quad (4)$$

We assume that both material types 1 and 2 share the same bulk elastic modulus K with distinct complex shear moduli μ_1 and μ_2 as in Bonifasi-Lista and Cherkaev [2009], Cherkaev [2019]. This simplification allows us to utilize the ACM in a single complex variable and analyze the deviatoric characteristics of the composite matrix/inclusion geometry. With this in mind, the local elasticity tensor can be written as $\mathbf{C} = 2K\mathbf{\Lambda}_h + 2\mu_2(1 - (1/s)\chi_1)\mathbf{\Lambda}_s$ with the material contrast variable $s = 1/(1 - \mu_1/\mu_2)$. A resolvent representation of $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s$ can be obtained by substituting this expression for \mathbf{C} into the equilibrium equation $\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}) = 0$ and taking its deviatoric projection Cherkaev and Bonifasi-Lista [2011], Cherkaev [2019]:

$$\chi_1\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s = s(sI - \chi_1\Gamma\chi_1)^{-1}\chi_1\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0, \quad \Gamma = \mathbf{\Lambda}_s : \nabla^S \left(\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\mu_2}\mathbf{\Lambda}_h + \mathbf{\Lambda}_s \right) : \nabla^S \right)^{-1} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{\Lambda}_s. \quad (5)$$

The constant strain term $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0$ comes from the deviatoric projection of the representation $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^0 + \nabla^S \vec{\phi}$, where $\vec{\phi}$ is a vector perturbation and $\langle \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s \rangle = \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0$.

Consider the random geometric setting and let (Ω, P) be a probability space with underlying sigma-algebra of P -measurable sets and $\omega \in \Omega$ labeling the geometric realization of the random medium with local elasticity $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}(x, \omega)$ with $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The effective complex elasticity tensor \mathbf{C}^* of the composite can be defined as Milton [2002], Cherkaev and Bonifasi-Lista [2011], Cherkaev [2019]

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle = \mathbf{C}^* : \langle \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \rangle. \quad (6)$$

Here, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ are stationary random fields and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes ensemble averaging over all possible locally isotropic geometric realizations. We define the average deviatoric stress and strain as $\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s \rangle = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s^0$, $\langle \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s \rangle = \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0$ and applying $\mathbf{\Lambda}_s$ to equation (6) defines the effective viscoelasticity of the composite as

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s \rangle = 2\mu^*\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0. \quad (7)$$

The constant strain field $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0$ can be written as $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0 = \epsilon_s^0 \mathbf{a}_k$ where ϵ_s^0 is the strength of the constant strain field and \mathbf{a}_k is a 2×2 tensor basis element Cherkaev [2019],

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{a}_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{a}_3 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

It is clear that \mathbf{a}_1 spans the volumetric space and $\{\mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3\}$ spans the deviatoric space. With this in mind, it is suitable to take $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0 = \epsilon_s^0 \mathbf{a}_2$ or $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0 = \epsilon_s^0 \mathbf{a}_3$. Since $\mu^* \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0 = \langle \mu_2(1 - \frac{1}{s}\chi_1)\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s \rangle$, we can substitute in the resolvent representation (5) for $\chi_1\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s$ to obtain

$$\frac{\mu^*}{\mu_2} = 1 - F(s), \quad F(s) = \langle R_s \chi_1 \mathbf{a}_k : \mathbf{a}_k \rangle, \quad (9)$$

where $R_s = (sI - G)^{-1}$ is the resolvent operator of $G = \chi_1\Gamma\chi_1$. The key to the analytic continuation method is the Stieltjes integral representation Cherkaev and Bonifasi-Lista [2011], Cherkaev [2019]

$$F(s) = 1 - \frac{\mu^*}{\mu_2} = \int_0^1 \frac{d\nu(\lambda)}{s - \lambda}, \quad (10)$$

which follows from applying the spectral theorem to (9). The measure ν is the spectral measure of the operator G and $F(s) = \langle \chi_1\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^0 \rangle / (s(\epsilon_s^0)^2)$.

While the measure ν can include discrete and/or continuous components Milton [2002], it reduces to a weighted sum of Dirac δ -functions $\delta(\lambda - \lambda_j)$ for discrete media such as a discrete viscoelastic network or discretization of continuum media suitable for numerical computation. Here, we investigate effective transport properties of square, two-component matrix-inclusion networks in 2D of size L . In this setting, $G = \chi_1\Gamma\chi_1$ is a real-symmetric matrix of size $N = 3L^2$, χ_1 is a diagonal matrix with 1's and 0's along the diagonal corresponding to elasticity type, and Γ is a symmetric matrix constructed from periodic finite difference representations of ∇^S , $\nabla \cdot$, and discretized versions of $\mathbf{\Lambda}_h$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}_s$. The L^2 term in N is a result of our two-dimensional square setting, while the factor of 3 in N arises from the 3 "directions" \mathbf{a}_k ,

$k = 1, 2, 3$ that the tensor fields $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ occupy. The measure ν is determined by the eigenvalues λ_j and eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j of $N_1 \times N_1$ submatrices of G with rows and columns corresponding to the diagonal components $[\chi_1]_{jj} = 1$, with

$$d\nu(\lambda) = \sum_j m_j \delta(\lambda - \lambda_j) d\lambda, \quad m_j = |\mathbf{v}_j : \chi_1 \mathbf{a}_k|^2, \quad (11)$$

$j = 1, \dots, N_1$, and $N_1 \approx p_1 N$ (total number of type 1 bonds) Murphy et al. [2015, 2024]. In this case, equations (5) and (10) become finite sums with

$$F(s) = 1 - \frac{\mu^*}{\mu_2} = \sum_j \frac{m_j}{s - \lambda_j}, \quad \chi_1 \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s = s \sum_j \frac{\sqrt{m_j}}{s - \lambda_j} \mathbf{v}_j, \quad (12)$$

given explicitly in terms of the λ_j and eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j of G Murphy et al. [2015, 2024].

Equation (12) provides a direct link between localized tensor-valued eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j and eigenmodes of $\chi_1 \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s$ with large magnitudes in confined spatial regions, while extended eigenvectors correspond to fields extending throughout the network.

2.3 Vector-tensor equivalence

We establish here an isometry between vectors and higher rank tensors, not unlike Voigt notation or other engineering standards. This isometry, introduced in Cherkav [2019] to derive the Stieltjes analytic representation of the effective shear properties of viscoelastic composites, analogously to the electromagnetic case, will be used extensively in the matrix representation of $\chi_1 \Gamma \chi_1$. The purpose of this utility is to create a representation of the tensor-valued fields and projections that are amenable to the established computational methods demonstrated in Murphy et al. [2015], Morison et al. [2022], Murphy et al. [2024]. The tensor basis $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3\}$ given in (8) is uniquely suited for numerical computation of the discrete sums (12) in this elastic setting. The basis $\{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3\}$ is orthonormal with respect to contraction, $\mathbf{a}_i : \mathbf{a}_j = \delta_{ij}$, and hence any symmetric 2×2 matrix \mathbf{b} can be represented as $\mathbf{b} = \sum_{i=1}^3 b_i \mathbf{a}_i$ where $b_i = \mathbf{b} : \mathbf{a}_i$ which establishes an isometry between symmetric 2×2 matrices and \mathbb{R}^3 . Since the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and strain $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ are symmetric 2×2 matrices, we can thus write

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \sigma_k \mathbf{a}_k, \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \epsilon_k \mathbf{a}_k. \quad (13)$$

with $\sigma_j = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \mathbf{a}_j$ and likewise for $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$.

We can now choose to represent $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ as vectors in \mathbb{R}^3 that is reminiscent of the tensor basis $\{\mathbf{a}_k\}$:

$$\vec{\sigma} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} + \sigma_{21} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \vec{\epsilon} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{11} - \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{12} + \epsilon_{21} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

With this representation, it should be understood that σ_k, ϵ_k are the coefficients of stress and strain that lie in the ‘‘direction’’ \mathbf{a}_k . Relating this to the standard basis $\{\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3\}$ in \mathbb{R}^3 , we can summarize this notation via

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \sigma_k \mathbf{a}_k, \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \epsilon_k \mathbf{a}_k \quad (15)$$

$$\vec{\sigma} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \sigma_k \vec{e}_k, \quad \vec{\epsilon} = \sum_{k=1}^3 \epsilon_k \vec{e}_k. \quad (16)$$

This interchangeability between \vec{e}_k and \mathbf{a}_k allows for advantageous representations of the fourth rank tensors $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_h$ and $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_s$. Since $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_h$ and $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_s$ are projections onto the span of $\{\mathbf{a}_1\}$ and $\{\mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3\}$, respectively, they can be represented as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_h = \mathbf{a}_1 \otimes \mathbf{a}_1 \longrightarrow \Lambda_h = \vec{e}_1 \vec{e}_1^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Lambda}_s = \mathbf{a}_2 \otimes \mathbf{a}_2 + \mathbf{a}_3 \otimes \mathbf{a}_3 \longrightarrow \Lambda_s = \vec{e}_2 \vec{e}_2^T + \vec{e}_3 \vec{e}_3^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Here, we have used an un-bolded font to represent the 3×3 matrix representations of fourth-rank tensors. With this in mind, the stiffness tensor takes the form

$$C = 2K\Lambda_h + 2\mu\Lambda_s = \begin{bmatrix} 2K & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\mu & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2\mu \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

Finally, the basis $\{\mathbf{a}_k\}$ allows us to write the constitutive relation $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ instead as the standard matrix-vector product $\vec{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = C(K, \mu)\vec{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$. With these alterations, the computation of the tensor fields $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ fall in line with previous established methods for computing vector fields (such as the electric field \vec{E} in the electromagnetic case, see Morison et al. [2022], Golden et al. [2023]).

2.4 Matrix representation of G

Since the foundation of the analytic continuation method rests on the spectral theorem, it is imperative that the matrix $G = \chi_1 \Gamma \chi_1$ be real-symmetric, or Hermitian in the discrete setting. In this section, we construct a Hermitian representation of G suitable for numerical computation of the discrete sums in (12) which makes use of the vector-tensor equivalence established in the previous section.

We consider an $L \times L$ viscoelastic network or an $L \times L$ discretization of a continuum composite. Consider a finite, two-component bond lattice on $\mathbb{Z}_L^2 \subset \mathbb{Z}^2$ determined by the probability space (Ω, P) , where

$$\mathbb{Z}_L^2 = \{\vec{x} \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \mid 1 \leq x_i \leq L, i = 1, 2\} \quad (20)$$

Define a bijective mapping Θ from the 2-dimensional set \mathbb{Z}_L^2 onto the 1-dimensional set $\mathbb{N}_L \subset \mathbb{N}$, $\Theta : \mathbb{Z}_L^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_L$ given by Murphy et al. [2015, 2024]

$$\mathbb{N}_L = \{i \in \mathbb{N} \mid i \leq 3L^2\}, \quad \Theta(\vec{x}) = x_1 + (x_2 - 1)L \quad (21)$$

and so Θ maps the first point $(1, 1)$ in a 2D grid to 1 and the last point (L, L) in a 2D grid to L^2 . Going forward, we denote the discretized representations of second and fourth rank tensors through the bijection Θ by using hat $(\hat{\cdot})$ notation. Under the bijection Θ , the components $\epsilon_j(\vec{x}, \omega)$ of the vectorized strain field $\vec{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ are mapped to the vector-valued functions $\epsilon_j(\vec{x}, \omega) \mapsto \hat{\epsilon}_j(\omega) = (\epsilon_j^1(\omega), \dots, \epsilon_j^{L^2}(\omega))$ so that

$$\Theta(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\vec{x}, \omega)) = \hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\omega) = (\hat{\epsilon}_1(\omega), \hat{\epsilon}_2(\omega), \hat{\epsilon}_3(\omega)) \in \mathbb{C}^N, \quad N = 3L^2. \quad (22)$$

Moreover, Θ maps the standard (now tensor) basis vector $\vec{e}_1 = (1, 0, 0) \in \mathbb{Z}^3$ to the vector $\hat{e}_1 = (\vec{1}, \vec{0}, \vec{0}) \in \mathbb{Z}^N$ (and similar for \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3), where $\vec{1}$ and $\vec{0}$ are vectors of ones and zeros of length L^2 .

On \mathbb{N}_L , the characteristic function $\chi_1(\vec{x}, \omega)$ is represented by a block diagonal matrix,

$$\hat{\chi}_1(\omega) = \text{diag}(\hat{\chi}_1^1(\omega), \hat{\chi}_1^2(\omega), \hat{\chi}_1^3(\omega)), \quad \hat{\chi}_2(\omega) = I_N - \hat{\chi}_1(\omega) \quad (23)$$

where I_N is the $N \times N$ identity matrix. Each $\hat{\chi}_1^j(\omega)$ is a diagonal matrix of 1's and 0's of size $L^2 \times L^2$ and so $\hat{\chi}_1(\omega)$ is of size $N \times N$. $\hat{\chi}_1(\omega)$ acts on $\hat{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\omega)$ via each $\hat{\chi}_1^j(\omega)$ operating on $\hat{\epsilon}_j(\omega)$. The 1's and 0's along the diagonal of $\hat{\chi}_1^j(\omega)$ correspond to the locations of the type 1 material interpreted through the bijection Θ . In this way, $\hat{\chi}_1^j(\omega)$ "zeroes out" the components of $\hat{\epsilon}_j(\omega)$ that do not correspond to the type 1 material, and similarly for $\hat{\chi}_2^j(\omega)$.

The projections Λ_h and Λ_s attain the following representations through Θ :

$$\hat{\Lambda}_h = \begin{bmatrix} I_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} \\ 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} \\ 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{\Lambda}_s = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} \\ 0_{L^2} & I_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} \\ 0_{L^2} & 0_{L^2} & I_{L^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

where 0_{L^2} is a matrix of zeros. As expected, $\hat{\Lambda}_h + \hat{\Lambda}_s = I_N$. We remark here that the specific form of the tensor basis (8) enables the diagonality of $\hat{\Lambda}_h$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_s$ which allows them to commute with $\hat{\chi}_1$ in the following section. Following Cherkhev [2019], the finite difference representation of the symmetrized gradient ∇^S takes the form

$$\nabla^S = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} \partial_x & \partial_y \\ \partial_x & -\partial_y \\ \partial_y & \partial_x \end{bmatrix} \longrightarrow \hat{\nabla} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} C_x & C_y \\ C_x & -C_y \\ C_y & C_x \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

For our purposes, the $L^2 \times L^2$ matrices C_i represent finite, periodic forward difference matrices and we have dropped the superscript S notation for the discretized symmetrized gradient. It is straightforward to check that this form correctly relates displacement to strain in our chosen basis, $\hat{\nabla} \vec{u} = \vec{\epsilon}$, and also satisfies the corresponding adjoint property $(\hat{\nabla})^T = -\text{Div}$. With these elements in place, we are ready to construct the Hermitian matrix $\hat{\chi}_1 \hat{\Gamma} \hat{\chi}_1$.

Let $\hat{\Lambda}_{a,b} = a\hat{\Lambda}_h + b\hat{\Lambda}_s$. Since $\hat{\Lambda}_h$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_s$ are diagonal and mutually orthogonal, we have that for any scalars $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{C}$, $\hat{\Lambda}_{a,b}\hat{\Lambda}_{c,d} = \hat{\Lambda}_{c,d}\hat{\Lambda}_{a,b} = \hat{\Lambda}_{ac,bd}$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_{a,b}^T = \hat{\Lambda}_{a,b}$. Then the operator Γ given in (5), interpreted through Θ , can be written as

$$\hat{\Gamma} = \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1} \hat{\nabla} (\hat{\nabla}^T \hat{\Lambda}_{k_2,1} \hat{\nabla})^{-1} \hat{\nabla}^T \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1}, \quad (26)$$

where $k_2 = K/\mu_2$ and the inversion now represents standard matrix inversion. Next, we replace $\hat{\Lambda}_{k_2,1}$ with $\hat{\Lambda}_{\sqrt{k_2},1}^2$ to rewrite (26) as

$$\hat{\Gamma} = \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1} \hat{\nabla} \left((\hat{\Lambda}_{\sqrt{k_2},1} \hat{\nabla})^T (\hat{\Lambda}_{\sqrt{k_2},1} \hat{\nabla}) \right)^{-1} \hat{\nabla}^T \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1}. \quad (27)$$

Since $\hat{\Lambda}_{\sqrt{k_2},1} \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1} = \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1}$, we can pre- and post-multiply $\hat{\Gamma}$ by $\hat{\Lambda}_{\sqrt{k_2},1}$ without altering it. Using the commutivity and symmetry of $\hat{\Lambda}_{a,b}$, (27) then becomes

$$\hat{\Gamma} = \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1} \hat{N} (\hat{N}^T \hat{N})^{-1} \hat{N}^T \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1}, \quad \hat{N} = \hat{\Lambda}_{\sqrt{k_2},1} \hat{\nabla}. \quad (28)$$

We can further simplify $\hat{\Gamma}$ by performing singular value decomposition (SVD) on the matrix \hat{N} . SVD allows us to write $\hat{N} = U \Sigma V^T$, where U and V are orthogonal matrices of size $N \times N$ and $2L^2 \times 2L^2$ satisfying $U^T U = U U^T = I_N$ and $V^T V = V V^T = I_{2L^2}$. Σ is a diagonal matrix of size $N \times 2L^2$ with diagonal components consisting of the positive singular values σ_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, of the matrix \hat{N} satisfying $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_\rho > 0$ and $\sigma_{\rho+1} = \sigma_{\rho+2} = \dots = \sigma_n = 0$, where ρ is the rank of \hat{N} .

Write the matrices U and V in block form as $U = [U_1, U_0]$ and $V = [V_1, V_0]$, where U_1 and V_1 are the columns of U and V corresponding to the strictly positive singular values in Σ . Letting Σ_1 be the diagonal part of Σ consisting of the strictly positive singular values in Σ , we can write $\hat{N} = U_1 \Sigma_1 V_1^T$. Using the property $U_1^T U_1 = I_\rho$, (28) becomes $\hat{\Gamma} = \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1} U_1 U_1^T \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1}$. Since $\hat{\Gamma}$ is sandwiched by $\hat{\chi}_1$, we utilize the symmetry and commutivity of $\hat{\chi}_1$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_{0,1}$ to obtain the final Hermitian form of $\hat{\chi}_1 \hat{\Gamma} \hat{\chi}_1$:

$$\hat{\chi}_1 \hat{\Gamma} \hat{\chi}_1 = \hat{\chi}_1^s \hat{\Gamma}^s \hat{\chi}_1^s \quad (29)$$

$$\hat{\Gamma}^s \equiv U_1 U_1^T, \quad \hat{\chi}_1^s \equiv \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1} \hat{\chi}_1 = \hat{\chi}_1 \hat{\Lambda}_{0,1} = \text{diag}(0_{L^2}, \hat{\chi}_1^2, \hat{\chi}_1^3). \quad (30)$$

This representation illustrates that $\hat{\Gamma}^s$ is a projection onto the range of $(\sqrt{k_2} \mathbf{\Lambda}_h + \mathbf{\Lambda}_s) : \nabla^S$ and $\hat{\chi}_1^s$ is the deviatoric projection onto the type 1 material. The spectral measure weights m_j shown in the sums in equation (12) have value zero, $m_j = 0$, for eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j satisfying $\hat{\chi}_1 \mathbf{v}_j = 0$ having eigenvalues $\lambda_j = 0$ Murphy et al. [2015, 2024]. Consequently, the non-trivial contributions of the sums in (12) are over eigenvalues and eigenvectors of $N_1 \times N_1$ sub-matrices of $\hat{\Gamma}^s$ associated with the indices i where $[\hat{\chi}_1]_{ii} = 1$, where N_1 is the number of non-zero diagonal entries in $\hat{\chi}_1$ Murphy et al. [2015, 2024]. Henceforth, when we discuss eigenvalues λ_j and eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j of the matrix G , we are referring to these non-trivial eigen-pairs. Versions of this framework which provide resolvent and spectral characterizations of ϵ_h , ϵ , composite materials with distinct bulk moduli K_i , as well as the spatially three-dimensional version of the basis (8), will be covered in subsequent works.

3 Results

We begin this section with a demonstration of deviatoric strain fields, computed using the spectral decomposition of G and (12), which showcases the complex interaction between material geometry, matrix-inclusion viscoelastic impedance contrast, and impinging wave frequency ω . This frequency-dependent localization/delocalization transition of strain fields ϵ_s is shown for different values of ω (which are realized by the model through the material contrast variable $s(\omega)$) in Figure 2. The localized fields correspond to frequencies where elastic energy is trapped within or near inclusions, analogous to the evanescent fields observed near surface plasmon resonances in metal-dielectric composites Morison et al. [2022]. The extended fields correspond to frequencies where the composite transmits elastic waves coherently through the matrix. The frequency dependence of the localization profile of the composite material is dependent on

Figure 2: **Periodic and random phononic crystal microgeometry and Anderson localization of fields.** Periodic and random arrangements of circular inclusions for two different lattice constants a in a matrix host with system size $L = 150$. Geometry is illustrated by rendering bonds (or pixels) corresponding to $\chi_1 = 1$ and omitting $\chi_2 = 1$ bonds. The scalar fields depicted are the off-diagonal components of the strain field $|1/\sqrt{2}(\epsilon_{12} + \epsilon_{21})|$ (or equivalently, $|\epsilon_3|$) in log 10 scale using $\epsilon_s^0 = \mathbf{a}_2 + \mathbf{a}_3$ where cool and warm colors correspond to near-zero and large values of the strain field $|\chi_1 \epsilon_s|$ or stress $|\chi_1 \sigma_s|$. The differences in the values of $|\chi_1 \epsilon_s|$ between the top and bottom rows are solely due to the frequency ω dependent material properties for different values of ω . Each distinct geometry permits certain frequencies ω to propagate through the spatial region (extended, bottom) while isolating and concentrating others in a small region (localized, top). The inverse participation ratio (IPR) of the strain field given in Figure 4 offers a further quantitative description of this geometric-frequency localization phenomenon.

the microgeometry of the material. We investigate these transitions and other phenomena through mathematical and physical quantities such as the spectral measure ν of the matrix G , correlations of its eigenvalues, localization of its eigenvectors, phase and magnitude of μ^* , and the localization and intensity of ϵ_s .

In the following experiments, we capture effective strain behavior of a broad range of wave frequencies and constituent material parameters by varying the contrast variable $s(\omega)$ along the interval $\text{Re}(s) \in [0, 1]$ while keeping $\text{Im}(s) \ll 1$. As the frequency changes and $s(\omega)$ sweeps across the complex plane, the spectral measure ν , distribution of eigenvalues, and localization of eigenvectors govern the phase and magnitude of μ^* as well as the intensity of ϵ_s according to the formulas in Eq. (12). Keeping these formulas in mind, we call resonant frequencies the values of ω where the masses m_j of ν are largest or where there's a large density of eigenvalues λ_j with moderate to large values of m_j .

For the periodic systems shown on the left side of Figure 3, the spectral measure ν is plotted as the measure weights m_j versus the associated eigenvalues λ_j . There is a clear delineation between spectral weights $m_j \lesssim 10^{-20}$ (numerically zero) and larger weights $10^{-10} \lesssim m_j \lesssim 10^0$ which significantly contribute to the sums in (12). For $s(\omega)$ near the unit interval $[0, 1]$, primary contributions to the sums are due to *resonances* in the spectral measure ν near $s(\omega)$. Resonances can be due to isolated spectral measure components with relatively large weights m_j or a high density of relatively small or large weights. As in the setting of electrical conductivity Bergman and Stroud [1992], the high density of relatively large weights m_j associated with eigenvalues $\lambda_j \approx 0$ is an indication that the matrix phase is connected on macroscopic scales. As the lattice constant a decreases (and the *scale* increases), the spectral measure resonances become more isolated and eigenvalue density plays less of a role in the resonances of ν . In contrast, for the random systems on the right side of Figure 3, as the lattice constant a decreases (and the *disorder* increases), sharp resonances in the spectral measure spread out and eigenvalue density plays more of a role. We show later using techniques of random matrix theory that, as the random system becomes increasingly disordered, the eigenvalues become increasingly correlated, with an increase in eigenvalue level repulsion causing high eigenvalue density resonances in ν to broaden and spread out.

The Inverse Participation Ratio (IPR) of eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j characterizes vector localization phenomenon. For an N_1 -dimensional unit vector \mathbf{u} it is given by $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_i u_i^4$, where u_i is the i th component of the vector \mathbf{u} , $i = 1, \dots, N_1$. Two limiting cases illustrate the meaning of $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{u})$: (i) a normalized vector with only one component $u_i = 1$ has

Figure 3: **Order and scaling sensitivity of the spectral measure and eigenvector localization.** Spectral measure weights m_j (top row) and eigenvector inverse participation ratio $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{v}_j)$ plotted for 3 different lattice constants a using a system size $L = 150$. The masses m_j (top row) of the spectral measure ν are plotted versus eigenvalues $0 \leq \lambda_j \leq 1$ of the matrix G . Similarly, the IPR values of the eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j (bottom row) of G are plotted versus eigenvalues. The horizontal red lines indicate the limiting IPR value $3/N_1$ for eigenvectors of the Gaussian orthogonal ensemble (GOE).

$\text{IPR}(\mathbf{u}) = 1$ and (ii) a vector with identical components $u_i = 1/\sqrt{N_1}$ has $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{u}) = 1/N_1$. Eigenvectors of matrices in the Gaussian Orthogonal Ensemble (GOE) are known to be highly extended with mean asymptotic IPR value is $\text{IPR}_{\text{GOE}} = 3/N_1$ Murphy et al. [2017], Guhr et al. [1997].

The bottom row of Figure 3 displays the IPR for the eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_j , $j = 1, \dots, N_1$, of G as a function of the eigenvalues λ_j , which we denote $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{v}_j)$. Highly extended eigenvectors are near the IPR value associated with the GOE, indicated by the horizontal red line $\sim 10^{-4}$. Highly localized eigenvectors have IPR values $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{v}_j) \sim 10^0$. Regions where $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{v}_j)$ suddenly changes from localized to extended for small changes of λ_j are called *mobility edges*. For periodic geometry the eigenvectors become increasingly extended, approaching the GOE limit, as the lattice constant a decreases (and the *scale* increases). The mobility edges shown in Figure 3 roughly coincide with resonances in the spectral measure and regions of higher eigenvalue density, indicating correlations between the eigenvalues and eigenvectors. These features become more prominent with decreasing a . For random media, the $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{v}_j)$ has similar localization and mobility edge features but the eigenvectors remain relatively localized. We note that the measure weights m_j and $\text{IPR}(\mathbf{v}_j)$ values are roughly equal in number, N_1 , for each plot; the appearance of less points for larger lattice constants a is due to the spectrum accumulating at the spectral endpoints $\lambda = 0, 1$.

The Stieltjes sum for μ^* and eigenvector expansion of $\chi_1 \epsilon_s$ in Equation (12) links the resonance behavior of the spectral measure ν to resonances in μ^* and to "hot spots" in $\chi_1 \epsilon_s$. More specifically, when $s(\omega)$ is close to a resonance in ν on the unit interval $[0, 1]$, this gives rise to large values in $F(s)$, hence μ^* , and results in commensurate values in $\chi_1 \epsilon_s$. This is clearly shown in Figure 4, for the same geometries as before with $\text{Re}s(\omega)$ and $\text{Im}s(\omega) = 0.001$. The resonances in the modulus of μ^*/μ_2 closely follow resonances in ν . For the periodic lattices (left side), at the resonant frequencies both ν and $|\mu^*|$ are sharply peaked.

At these resonant frequencies in periodic lattices, μ^* also undergoes dramatic switches in phase from $\sim 0^\circ$ to $\sim 180^\circ$. These phase switches correspond to an 'elastic transition' where the effective material response changes from elastic (energy-storing) to viscoelastic (energy-dissipating) characterized by a negative effective shear modulus. This effect is especially pronounced for the $a = 1/15$ case. At the resonant frequencies where $|\mu^*|$ peaks and the phase reaches 180° , the composite exhibits a large negative effective shear modulus, responding strongly and out of phase with the applied strain which is analogous to the inductive (metallic) response at surface plasmon resonances in metal-dielectric composites Morison et al. [2022], Bergman and Stroud [1992]. At the intervening trough frequencies where $|\mu^*|$ is small and the phase returns to 0° , the composite responds weakly and in phase, behaving as a compliant but conventional elastic material — analogous to band gap frequencies in photonic crystals where the material acts as an effective insulator Bergman and Stroud [1992]. For random media (right side), such phenomena are less clear, with the phase of μ^* seemingly randomly distributed between 0° and 180° for each lattice constant with no obvious pattern.

The presence of \mathbf{v}_j in the eigenvector expansion of $\chi_1 \epsilon_s$ in (12) introduces a spatial modulation that complicates the connection between spectral measure resonances and "hot spots" in $\chi_1 \epsilon_s$. When $s(\omega)$ is close to a resonance in ν , the

Figure 4: **Frequency dependence of effective viscoelasticity and strain field localization.** Relative effective complex viscoelasticity μ^*/μ_2 modulus and phase and inverse participation ratio (IPR) of the deviatoric strain field, $|\chi_1\epsilon_s|$, normalized to unity, and plotted versus $0 \leq \text{Re } s \leq 1$ with $\text{Im } s = 0.001$ for three different lattice constants a for periodic and random geometries.

large coefficients in the expansion amplify the contribution of the associated eigenvectors, which governs both the magnitude of μ^* and the spatial structure of $\chi_1\epsilon_s$. Since resonances in ν are determined only by composite geometry, this suggests that incident wave frequencies with $s(\omega)$ near a resonance are associated with the localization of the wave within the composite microgeometry. Similarly, frequencies with $s(\omega)$ away from all resonances in ν are associated with waves extended throughout the composite microgeometry. In other words, the composite microgeometry determines which wave frequencies propagate through the medium on macroscopic length scales and which wave frequencies get localized within the composite medium. However, the spatial dependence of the \mathbf{v}_j can lead to cancellations that disrupt this correspondence. A clear example of this is the ubiquitous concurrence of extended $\chi_1\epsilon_s$ for $s(\omega) \approx 0$ corresponding to a resonance in the measure ν and $|\mu^*|$. When $s(\omega)$ is close to a resonance in the spectral measure, these large coefficients in the eigenfunction expansion of $\chi_1\epsilon_s$ govern which eigenfunctions play a dominant role in the expansion.

A close inspection of the periodic setting indicates that mobility edges in $\text{IPR}(\chi_1\epsilon_s)$ typically occur just before and just after resonances in μ^* . These mobility edges, which accompany a sudden increase in the number of localized eigenvectors, mark transitions between propagating and non-propagating frequency regimes analogous to band edges in photonic crystals, where mobility edges separate extended Bloch-like states from evanescent ones. This behavior indicates that the composite's ability to transmit or trap elastic energy is highly sensitive to frequency near these critical values. Decreasing the lattice constant a leads to greater band structure in the periodic systems, suggesting that finite-size effects play a critical role in the formation and visibility of band gaps.

As is the case for the modulus and phase of μ^* , the field localization $\text{IPR}(\chi_1\epsilon_s)$ for disordered geometries does not exhibit similar band structure or mobility edges as the periodic geometries do. For decreasing lattice constant a , the strain fields on average become more extended. However, we observe that random systems are more localized on average compared to periodic systems across the given scales, a characteristic normally attributed to wave interference and Anderson localization. While the disordered systems lack the tunable resonant structure of their periodic counterparts, the greater average localization of strain fields suggests these systems are more effective at trapping elastic energy across a broad frequency range, albeit without the frequency selectivity afforded by band structure.

3.1 Random matrix theory analysis

Statistical quantities for the eigenvalues λ_j of G provide qualitative insights into the chaos and universality occurring in our geometric systems. The nearest neighbor eigenvalue spacing distribution (ESD) $P(z)$, which provides short-range correlations of eigenvalues, was initially introduced in random matrix theory to describe fluctuations of characteristic quantities for random systems, but has since accurately described quantities for non-random systems with sufficient complexity. For highly correlated Wigner-Dyson spectra exhibited by, for example, the Gaussian orthogonal ensemble of real-symmetric random matrices, the ESD is accurately approximated by Wigner's surmise, $P(z) = (\pi z/2)\exp(-\pi z^2/4)$, which illustrates eigenvalue repulsion, vanishing linearly as spacings $z \rightarrow 0$. In contrast, the ESD for uncorrelated Poisson spectra, $P(z) = \exp(-z)$, allows for significant level degeneracy. The ESD probes

Figure 5: **Eigenvalue spacing distributions.** Normalized eigenvalue spacing distributions (ESD) $P(z)$ for periodic and random geometries with varying lattice constants a from $a = 0.5$ to $a = 0.05$. Periodic and random arrangements at small scales ($a = 0.5, 0.2$) exhibit simple, integrable dynamics with energy levels that are randomly spaced leading to $P(0) \sim 1$. At greater scales $a \leq 0.1$, long-range order in periodic systems continues to develop which counteracts the chaotic dynamics that dominate in random systems, leading to Wigner-Dyson statistics for the random systems and Poisson-like statistics maintaining in the periodic systems. While random realizations of unique geometries are easily generated for the random systems, periodic geometries required a small amount of noise for each statistical trial to produce the ESDs above and likely resulted in a small amount of eigenvalue repulsion reflected by $P(0) \lesssim 1$ for $a \leq 0.1$. Poisson and Wigner-Dyson distributions are shown as dashed lines for reference.

short-range correlations between eigenvalues and serves as a diagnostic for the degree of mode interaction in the system. Increasing level repulsion, as measured by the vanishing of $P(z)$ near $z = 0$, causes high-density resonances in the spectral measure to spread out, directly linking eigenvalue statistics to the broadening of spectral features observed in Figure 3.

Systems that exhibit Poisson statistics are associated with integrable, ordered systems. In such systems, the energy levels (or eigenfrequencies, in the case of acoustic and classical wave systems) are uncorrelated and behave like random points without any repulsion. Small spacings between these points are relatively common, which reflects the lack of interaction between modes of the system. On the other hand, Wigner-Dyson statistics are exhibited by systems which possess highly irregular, unpredictable dynamics (so-called chaotic systems). These systems are characterized by strong sensitivity to initial conditions with energy levels which exhibit strong correlations and level repulsion, meaning that the eigenvalues tend to avoid being too close to each other. This level repulsion arises from complex interaction between modes. In this regard, the eigenvalue spacing distribution serves as a proxy for how ordered a given system is. Here we draw connections between the relative scale (or lattice constant a) and degree of order in the system.

ESDs for the periodic and random geometries are given in Figure 5. This statistical quantity again showcases a clear distinction in behavior between both geometry classes across several scales. The periodic geometries exhibit Poisson statistics in their eigenvalue spacing regardless of scale, suggesting that the eigenmodes are extended Bloch waves that are regular and predictable. The sparsity of modes in small periodic systems naturally leads to Poisson statistics, as the modes are effectively independent. However, even in larger periodic systems, the dominant role of long-range order prevents the emergence of chaotic dynamics, so that the statistics remain Poisson-like. For random geometries, we observe a clear transition in eigenvalue statistics from Poisson to Wigner-Dyson as the scale is increased. At these increasing scales, the randomness of the system strengthens, which introduces chaotic dynamics, strong mode interactions, and level repulsion. At the minimal scale $a = 1/2$, the level of disorder is low enough that Poisson statistics emerge, resembling the periodic cases.

3.2 Scaling and order

The results presented in Figures 3 - 5 demonstrate a striking relationship between geometric order and scale which gives rise to distinct wave transport regimes. The scaling function $\beta(\gamma)$, which describes how wave transport properties change with system size, and the Thouless conductance $g \sim \gamma$ which is related to the effective shear modulus μ^* , offer

Figure 6: **Spectrum of order.** Periodic and random geometries with different lattice constants a arranged to obtain a spectrum of order. The degree of order is derived from the results of Figures 3 - 5, with maximum order being characterized by band structure and negative shear moduli, and maximum disorder characterized by Wigner-Dyson eigenvalue spacing statistics. These two endpoints of the spectrum meet at the transition point which is given by the lattice constant $a = 1$, since both classes of geometries are most similar here. We observe a smooth transition between both ends of the spectrum through this transition point which leads to the scale-induced spectrum of order for this class of phononic metamaterials.

further insight into these regimes. For periodic systems, $\beta(\gamma)$ and g are primarily frequency-dependent rather than scale-dependent. Within frequency bands where eigenstates are extended, g is large and $\beta(\gamma) \approx d - 2 = 0$, corresponding to the extended transport regime. Within band gaps, g becomes exponentially small with increasing system size and $\beta(\gamma) \approx \ln(\gamma) \ll 0$, corresponding to the localized (evanescent) regime. Increasing scale in periodic systems sharpens this frequency-dependent alternation between extended and localized regimes, as evidenced by the increasingly pronounced band structure and phase switching in μ^* for decreasing a , but does not change the fundamental character of the transport. The Poisson eigenvalue spacing statistics observed at all scales (Figure 5) reflect the integrability of the periodic structure rather than localization. In contrast, for disordered systems, $\beta(\gamma)$ and g are primarily scale-dependent. At smaller scales, the system size L is comparable to or smaller than the localization length ξ , leading to trapped waves and Poisson-like statistics characteristic of effectively independent modes. As the scale increases, the growing number of randomly placed scatterers strengthens the effective disorder, introducing chaotic mode interactions and level repulsion that drive the eigenvalue statistics toward Wigner-Dyson. This Poisson-to-Wigner-Dyson transition suggests that γ and g increase with scale, consistent with the system approaching a critical regime where $\beta(\gamma) \approx 0$ and modes transition from localized to extended character.

Thus, periodic and disordered systems achieve their respective transport properties through fundamentally different mechanisms: periodic systems derive their frequency-selective behavior from long-range structural order and integrability, while disordered systems exhibit scale-dependent transport governed by the competition between disorder-induced localization and emergent chaotic dynamics. These two contrasting geometric regimes meet at the smallest scale $a = 1$, where the periodic and random geometries are merely translated versions of each other and exhibit similar spectral characteristics of the matrix G and localization of fields. The observations here lead to a scale-induced "spectrum of order" which is illustrated in Figure 6.

4 Conclusion

The analytic continuation method is a powerful tool for understanding how composite microstructure governs elastic wave transport. We have demonstrated that the statistical behavior of the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the random operator $G = \chi_1 \Gamma \chi_1$ undergoes a transition that parallels Anderson localization in wave physics, despite the absence of any quantum, wave interference, or scattering effects. The eigenvalue statistics of G undergo a Poisson-to-Wigner-Dyson transition with increasing scale in disordered systems, driven by emergent chaotic mode interactions, while periodic systems maintain Poisson statistics at all scales due to their underlying integrability.

These two classes of systems offer complementary capabilities for wave control. Periodic composites provide frequency-selective behavior: well-defined band gaps for vibration isolation, mobility edges marking sharp transitions between propagating and evanescent regimes, and phase switching in μ^* signaling transitions to negative effective shear modulus which all become more pronounced with increasing system size. Disordered composites, by contrast, offer broadband energy trapping through spatially localized strain fields that persist across a wide frequency range, albeit without the tunability afforded by band structure. The "spectrum of order" connecting these two limits through the transition point at $a = 1$ provides a unified framework for navigating this design space.

Our results provide a unified framework for understanding how the scale-induced spectrum of order in phononic metamaterials determines their wave transport properties, offering insights for designing materials with tailored elastic wave propagation characteristics through careful control of geometric order, system size, and constituent material properties. Extensions of this framework to composites with distinct bulk moduli, three-dimensional geometries, and non-circular inclusion shapes would broaden the applicability of these results. Finally, the connection between the spectral properties of G and Anderson localization in wave physics, while striking, rests on statistical analogy rather than shared physical mechanisms. Together with analogous findings for electromagnetic transport in composites Murphy et al. [2017], Morison et al. [2022], these results suggest that Anderson-like spectral transitions are a robust feature of classical transport in heterogeneous media, transcending the specific physics of wave propagation.

Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge support from the US National Science Foundation through grants DMS-2136198 and DMS-2206171, and the Applied and Computational Analysis Program at the US Office of Naval Research through grants N00014-21-1-2909 and N00014-26-1-2114.

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